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CORPORATE TAX AND INVESTMENT OF INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study ascertained the effect of corporate tax on investment of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, using company income tax and tertiary education tax as the corporate tax. Ex post facto research design was adopted. Data were extracted from the sampled industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study employed multiple regression analysis to test the hypotheses. The study showed there is negative effects of company income tax indicate that high transactional and income-based tax burdens can reduce liquidity, increase operational costs, and limit the financial flexibility necessary for firms to undertake new investments or expand existing operations. The study revealed that tertiary education taxes have significant positive effect on net investing cash flow. Based on the results, the study recommended that the Ministry of Finance need to consider revising the scheduling and collection mechanisms of company income tax to reduce cash flow constraints on firms, since the significant negative effect on net investing cash flow indicates that current CIT obligations may limit the ability of firms to fund investment projects.

Keywords: Corporate tax, Investment, Company income tax and Tertiary education tax

Introduction

Corporate taxes may affect firm investment through several channels, primarily by influencing the amount of profit available for reinvestment and the expected return on new projects. Taxes on profits, such as company income tax and tertiary education tax in Nigeria, directly reduce retained earnings, which are a major source of internal financing for many firms. This is particularly important in developing economies where access to external finance may be limited due to high interest rates, underdeveloped capital markets, or strict lending conditions. When after tax profits decline, firms may postpone or scale down expansion plans, delay equipment purchases, or reduce spending on research and development. Empirical studies provide mixed evidence regarding these effects. Some studies indicate that higher tax obligations can significantly reduce corporate investment, particularly in sectors where tax burdens are heavy (Eyide et al., 2021; Amahalu, 2020; Abu et al., 2023).

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Compliance costs associated with multiple taxes can further strain financial and administrative resources, especially for small and medium sized enterprises. At the same time, tax revenue finances public goods such as transportation networks, power supply, legal systems, and education, all of which support business activity. Research has also highlighted that well-structured tax systems and supportive fiscal environments can enhance investment inflows when combined with stable macroeconomic conditions and effective infrastructure provision (Bhusal, 2025; Opuene & Akenbor, 2025). Therefore, the overall effect of corporate taxes on firm investment depends not only on tax rates but also on how the revenue is utilized and the broader economic environment in which firms operate.

A thriving economy depends on firms that are able to invest steadily in productive activities. When businesses expand their operations, acquire modern equipment, develop new products, and train their workforce, they increase output, create employment opportunities, and contribute to national income (Bhusal, 2025). In such a setting, taxation is structured in a manner that allows government to generate revenue without discouraging private sector growth.

In Nigeria, however, many firms operate under a tax system that includes multiple levies such as company income tax; value added tax, capital gains tax, and tertiary education tax (Ndah et al., 2024). Business owners frequently express concern that the cumulative burden of these taxes reduces the amount of profit available for reinvestment. For smaller industrial goods firms in particular, compliance requirements can be time consuming and financially demanding. Profit based taxes directly reduce retained earnings, which many companies rely on as their primary source of investment funds due to limited access to affordable credit. As a result, businesses may scale back expansion plans, postpone capital projects, or operate below their full productive capacity (Oshiole et al., 2024).

The consequences of this situation extend beyond individual firms to the broader economy. Reduced investment limits industrial growth, slows job creation, and weakens productivity improvements. When businesses are unable or unwilling to expand, unemployment may rise and income growth may stagnate, thereby affecting household welfare. Lower levels of private investment can also discourage foreign investors, who often consider the domestic business climate before committing capital (Olugbenga & Adepeju, 2025). In some cases, firms may resort to cost cutting measures that compromise product quality or workforce stability, while others may shift operations to jurisdictions perceived as more favorable. A prolonged decline in business investment can ultimately reduce the tax base itself, creating a cycle in which government revenue falls despite high tax rates. This situation highlights the need to examine how corporate taxation influences the investment capacity of firms and to determine whether the existing tax structure supports or constrains sustainable economic growth. This study therefore ascertains the effect of corporate tax on investment among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. To determine the effect of company income tax on net investing cash flow of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the effect of tertiary education tax on net investing cash flow of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

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Literature Review

Corporate tax

Corporate tax also plays a role in shaping the behavior of firms by influencing how they generate and allocate profit (Scarpa & Signori, 2023). Companies may consider the level of tax when making decisions about expansion, capital expenditure, and distribution of profits to shareholders (Bande et al., 2025). Higher taxes on profits can reduce the amount of funds available for reinvestment, while lower rates may encourage growth and entrepreneurial activity. Tax policies, therefore, have a direct link to business strategies and the overall economic performance of the industrial and commercial sectors. Finally, corporate tax serves as a mechanism to ensure that companies contribute fairly to the financial sustainability of the nation (Opune & Akenbor, 2025). It creates a structured relationship between the private sector and the government, where profits are partially directed toward collective societal needs. By adhering to corporate tax obligations, firms not only maintain legal compliance but also participate in the provision of essential public services that support economic stability and growth.

Company Income Tax

Corporate income tax is a fiscal duty that companies must pay to the government according to the profits they generate during a specific timeframe (Ndah et al., 2024). It is a levy imposed on a company's net profit, necessitating businesses to disclose their earnings and allocate a segment of their financial gains to government revenue. The tax guarantees that businesses functioning in the nation contribute to the financing of public services and infrastructure (Omodero, 2024). Distinct from other taxation methods that might aim at sales or consumption, corporate income tax zeroes in on the profits of businesses and organizations, connecting corporate profit directly to the public resources accessible.

It serves as an official method by which the government gathers funds from the private sector. Businesses must compute their taxable income, considering permissible expenses and deductions, and remit a designated rate established by legislation (Oshiole et al., 2024). This procedure creates an organized connection between private enterprise actions and public financial accountability. By requiring businesses to share a segment of their earnings, the tax spreads the financial responsibility for delivering public services among active organizations. Corporate income tax now affects both resident and non-resident companies operating in Nigeria according to their earnings. For the majority of businesses, the rate stands at thirty percent of taxable profit, although smaller firms with lesser revenue might be eligible for lower rates.

The income tax for companies also affects the financial planning and reporting of enterprises (Wang, 2022). Companies need to keep precise records of income and costs to guarantee adherence, thereby enhancing accountability and openness. The level of tax paid may fluctuate based on profitability, indicating both the firm's capacity to contribute and the government's economic strategies (Omodero, 2024).

Tertiary Education Tax

The tertiary education tax is a financial charge placed on businesses to fund higher education institutions in a nation (Onwughai & Ofili, 2025). It mandates that companies allocate a portion of their profits to finance universities, colleges, and other post-secondary institutions, guaranteeing that the private sector financially supports higher education. This tax represents a collective obligation of businesses and the government to enhance educational access, bolster academic infrastructure, and foster the growth of skilled human resources

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(Oshiole et al., 2022). It differs from standard corporate taxes as its aim is specifically linked to funding higher education instead of overall government spending.

The tax requires firms to engage in national educational growth by directly funding institutions that train future professionals (Habila et al., 2024). Entities need to determine their payable sum according to established rules and submit it to the appropriate government authority. With this approach, companies aid in the functioning of universities, the offering of scholarships, and the upkeep of educational infrastructure, connecting private sector gains to the progress of knowledge and education (Onwughai & Ofili, 2025).

The tax on tertiary education strengthens the link between economic progress and community advancement. Businesses indirectly profit from the tax due to the presence of skilled graduates joining the labor market, while higher education institutions receive a consistent stream of income (Ndah et al., 2024). The tax guarantees that the expenses associated with developing human capital are distributed among public and private entities, integrating accountability for educational advancement within the business sector (Onwughai & Ofili, 2025). The tax promotes clarity in financial disclosures and accountability within institutions. Businesses are required to keep track of earnings and tax contributions, while educational organizations oversee the allocation of funds to guarantee they are directed to the right programs.

Investment

The connection between investment and economic growth is important as business investments typically generate employment, enhance production capacity, and boost total output. The extent of investment may indicate confidence in the economic and regulatory landscape, affecting the choices of other companies, investors, and financial institutions (Bande et al., 2025). A company that consistently invests in its activities shows the capability and desire to aid in economic growth while pursuing financial gains. Investment acts as a key process that converts financial resources into both tangible and intangible assets, guaranteeing that businesses stay viable and able to produce future earnings (Osegbue et al., 2021).

Net investing cash flow indicates the overall cash a business spends or gains from dealings related to long-term assets over a defined time frame (Eze, 2021). It represents the flow of cash associated with the buying or selling of real estate, machinery, investments, or other long-term assets. This indicator demonstrates how an organization invests financial resources for growth and expansion or generates funds through asset sales (Gulo & Ginting, 2023).

Empirical studies

Ezejiofor and Ezinando (2026) investigated the impact of tax revenue on the economic development of Nigeria and South Africa during the period from 2001 to 2024. The statistical methods used included preliminary analysis tests like: Descriptive Statistics, Pearson Correlation, and Error Correction Model Regression Analysis. The study indicated that CIT positively influences the real gross domestic product in Nigeria, although this effect is statistically insignificant, while it has a negative and also statistically insignificant effect on South Africa's real gross domestic product. The research also found that VAT positively impacts real gross domestic product in Nigeria and South Africa, although the impact was not statistically significant in Nigeria, while it was significant in South Africa.

Bande et al. (2025) investigated how taxation affects corporate investment in publicly traded consumer goods firms in Nigeria. A retrospective research design was utilized, concentrating on 21 firms in the industry, from

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which 17 active companies were chosen for examination. Secondary data acted as the main source of information, and various regression techniques were utilized. The findings showed that the effective tax rate had a positive yet statistically insignificant impact on corporate investment, implying that changes in the tax burden did not significantly affect investment choices. Likewise, the cash effective tax rate exhibited a positive but not significant correlation with investment.

Opuene and Akenbor (2025) examined the link between corporate taxes and foreign investment in Nigeria from 2002 to 2024. Influenced by the Laffer Curve concept, which posits a nonlinear relationship between tax rates and revenue, the research employed an ex post facto approach and leveraged secondary data from the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, the Federal Inland Revenue Authority, and various international resources. The study utilized the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model for analysis. Results indicated that corporate tax rates possessed a significant positive effect on investment inflows, indicating that properly structured tax systems can support both domestic and foreign investment.

Ogbonnaya et al. (2025) analyzed the influence of company income tax (CIT) policies on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria over the period 1990 to 2023. The study employed an ex post facto design and utilized annual time-series data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, the Federal Inland Revenue Service, and World Bank publications. Both short-run and long-run Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) models were applied to examine the relationship between CIT and FDI. The results indicated that, in the long run, variables such as CIT rate, GDP growth, inflation, unemployment, and exchange rate significantly affect FDI inflows. In the short run, GDP growth, interest rate, government capital expenditure, and inflation volatility were identified as major determinants.

Stephen and Temitope (2025) investigated how taxation impacts the performance of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Secondary data were collected from the annual reports of publicly traded building and materials companies for the years 2015 to 2023. Panel regression analysis was utilized to assess the data. The results indicated that corporate income tax is a crucial factor influencing firm performance, demonstrating a negative coefficient at the 5 percent significance level.

Ajagun et al. (2025) examined the correlation between effective tax rates and return on equity for companies listed in Nigeria. The research utilized panel data extracted from company annual reports spanning a thirteen-year timeframe from 2010 to 2022. A quantitative method was utilized, and regression models were implemented on data from companies in various sectors. The findings indicated a notable inverse correlation between effective tax rates and return on equity, suggesting that increased tax liabilities generally diminish profitability, whereas reduced tax rates contribute to enhanced financial results. The research additionally investigated how elements like capital intensity and corporate governance could impact the efficacy of tax incentives.

Oluchi and Abel (2024) examined the impact of taxation on foreign direct investment inflows to Nigeria by analyzing time-series data from 2000 to 2020. Data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria, the Federal Inland Revenue Service, and the National Bureau of Statistics and analyzed through multiple regression utilizing the ordinary least squares method. Government tax revenue was broken down into corporate income tax, personal income tax, and value-added tax as independent variables, while FDI inflows were considered the

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dependent variable. The findings revealed that corporate income tax had a notable adverse impact on FDI, personal income tax demonstrated a negative yet insignificant correlation, while value-added tax had a positive and significant effect.

Eze et al. (2024) investigated how tax sheltering influences the investment spending of listed financial institutions in Nigeria. The study measured tax sheltering using effective tax rate, book–tax differences, and tax savings, while total investment expenditure served as the outcome variable. Data were obtained from the audited financial statements of 20 firms covering the period 2012 to 2022. The hypotheses were tested using the Multiple Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors model. Findings showed that the effective tax rate had a significant negative impact on investment expenditure, indicating that higher tax burdens reduce capital spending. Book–tax differences did not exhibit a statistically significant effect, whereas tax savings were found to encourage investment.

Omodero (2024) investigated the impact of Nigeria's tax system on equity capital investment by assessing six types of taxes levied on companies. Tax revenue data was retrieved from the Federal Inland Revenue Service, whereas equity investment information was collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin covering the years 2011 to 2020. Regression analysis indicated that capital gains tax and gas income tax had little impact on equity investment. Conversely, petroleum profit tax and corporate income tax exhibited significant adverse effects, indicating that substantial tax burdens deter equity financing. On the other hand, value-added tax and education tax were linked to notable and positive impacts on equity investment.

Adu (2024) examined how taxation affects the financial performance of certain listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Leveraging panel data from two companies between 2010 and 2019, the research utilized panel and linear regression methods to examine secondary data. The findings showed that taxation has a considerable influence on both investment and profitability, demonstrated by a probability value far beneath the 5 percent significance threshold. The research suggested that government strategies ought to be created to assist manufacturing companies instead of imposing heavy tax loads that may jeopardize their existence and, consequently, the larger economy.

Olaoye and Fasanmi (2024) investigated how taxation impacts the profitability of deposit money banks in various African nations, focusing specifically on corporate income tax and education tax. A retrospective design was utilized, concentrating on ten purposely chosen Nigerian banks out of a total of fourteen. Panel regression techniques were applied to analyze secondary data from audited financial statements from 2010 to 2019, following initial descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The findings showed that corporate income tax had a positive yet statistically inconsequential impact on profitability assessed through both return on equity and return on assets. Education tax showed a positive and significant effect on return on equity but a positive yet insignificant effect on return on assets.

Odusina (2023) examined the joint effect of corporate taxation and capital investment decisions on firm performance using an ex post facto design and secondary data from 61 purposely selected firms covering 2012 to 2020. Panel regression with fixed effects was employed for analysis. The results showed a positive and significant relationship between capital expenditure and return on assets, while another investment variable displayed a negative but insignificant relationship. Corporate taxation alone had a positive yet insignificant association with performance, and its individual impact on investment indicators was also weak.

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Eneisik et al. (2023) investigated the effect of company income tax on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. From a population of sixty firms, thirty were selected using purposive sampling. Secondary data covering 2006 to 2020 were obtained from audited financial statements. Panel least squares regression techniques were applied, with the fixed-effects model selected based on the Hausman test. Findings revealed that company income tax had a negative but insignificant effect on profitability, while capital gains tax showed a positive and significant influence. Tertiary education tax also had a negative but insignificant effect.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design, which is appropriate for analyzing causal effects when the independent variables have already occurred and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. In this study, corporate taxes includes company income tax and tertiary education tax, represent historical fiscal obligations imposed on listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population for this study consists of all the twelve industrial goods firms listed on the NGX as of 2024. According to NGX records, twelve (12) firms operate in this sector. These companies form the complete population from which the study draws its sample.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select firms with complete and consistent financial data covering the period 2015 to 2024. This resulted in a final sample of nine (9) firms. The purposive approach ensures that only firms with uninterrupted data records are analyzed, enabling a reliable longitudinal study.

Method of Data Collection

Secondary data were sourced from the audited annual financial statements of the selected firms, which are publicly accessible through the NGX website and individual corporate investor relations portals. The data cover the ten-year period from 2015 to 2024 and include reported amounts of company income tax, tertiary education tax and net investing cash flow.

Model Specification

However, the model above was modified as follows:

$$Y=f(X_1, \dots, X_5)$$

$$\text{NICF} = f(\text{CPT})$$

$$\text{NICF} = f(\text{CIT}, \text{TET})$$

$$\text{NICF}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(\text{CIT})_{it} + \beta_2(\text{TET})_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad \text{ii}$$

Where:

NICF_{it} = Net investing cash flow for firm i at time t

CIT_{it} = Company income tax for firm i at time t

TET_{it} = Tertiary education tax for firm i at time t

α = Intercept

β_1, β_2 = Coefficients of the respective independent variables

ϵ_{it} = Error term

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Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were first used to summarize central tendency, dispersion, and distribution patterns of all variables. Hypotheses were tested using Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares (EGLS).

The decision rule was based on a 5% significance level. Coefficients with p-values below 0.05 were considered significant, indicating that the corresponding tax type has a measurable effect on net investing cash flow, while p-values above 0.05 indicated no significant effect.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis

	NICF (₦'000)	CIT (₦'000)	TET (₦'000)
Mean	-19967953	11495306	1062389.
Median	-251459.0	103680.0	15489.00
Maximum	118485000	352898000	16424000
Minimum	-830938000	-315.0000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	95162722	46740324	3026975.
Skewness	-7.100405	5.436106	3.536711
Kurtosis	60.25300	35.60295	15.18364
Jarque-Bera	13048.39	4429.339	744.2789
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Observations	90	90	90

Source: E-views 10 Output (2026)

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for net investing cash flow (NICF), indicating that the chosen industrial goods companies in Nigeria had an average NICF of ₦19,967,953,000 during the examined period. This negative average indicates that, typically, the companies were spending more on investments than they were earning from investment returns, signifying net cash outflows. The highest NICF recorded was ₦118,485,000,000, indicative of times when companies made significant investments or saw exceptionally high inflows, whereas the lowest NICF of -₦830,938,000,000 underlines severe capital outflows in specific years. The standard deviation of ₦95,162,722,000 indicates a significant spread around the average, reflecting considerable variability in the investment practices among the companies. The skewness of -7.100 suggests a significantly left-skewed distribution, which indicates that extreme negative outliers are dragging the mean lower, while the kurtosis of 60.253 signifies a leptokurtic distribution characterized by sharp peaks and thick tails. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.000 indicates non-normality, yet the sample size of 90 observations may enable inferential statistics, per the central limit theorem, to still approximate normality for hypothesis testing.

The average company income tax (CIT) in Table 4.1 was ₦11,495,306,000, indicating that businesses, on average, contributed significant amounts in corporate taxes. The highest CIT payment reached ₦352,898,000,000, whereas the lowest of -₦315,000 suggests periodic tax corrections or reimbursements. The standard deviation of ₦46,740,324,000 indicates significant variation in CIT responsibilities. The distribution exhibits a positive skew of 5.436, suggesting that the majority of firms incurred lower expenses than the average, while a small number paid significantly high taxes. A kurtosis of 35.603 indicates a leptokurtic

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distribution characterized by heavy tails and a pronounced peak, revealing significant variations in tax payments among certain firms. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.000 signifies non-normality; however, the sample size of 90 observations could still permit dependable inferential testing.

For tertiary education tax (TET), Table 1 shows an average of ₦1,062,389,000, indicating that companies contributed slightly on average compared to other taxes. The highest TET payment reached ₦16,424,000,000, while the lowest was 0, indicating that some companies had no liabilities during specific intervals. The standard deviation of ₦3,026,975,000 shows significant variability considering the magnitude of certain payments. A skewness of 3.537 indicates a positively skewed distribution, where the majority of firms paid below the mean, while a small number of outliers paid much more. A kurtosis of 15.184 indicates a leptokurtic distribution characterized by heavy tails. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.000 indicates non-normality, but the central limit theorem implies that analyses with the 90 observations may still be statistically sound despite the dataset's skewness and kurtosis

Test of Hypotheses

Table 2 Test of Hypotheses

Dependent Variable: NICF

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)

Date: 04/12/26 Time: 09:11

Sample: 2015 2024

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 90

Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CIT	-1.486032	0.077717	-19.12103	0.0000
TET	24.77412	1.526644	16.22783	0.0000
C	-3458284.	253686.6	-13.63211	0.0000

Weighted Statistics

R-squared	0.971453	Mean dependent var	-1.430936
Adjusted R-squared	0.970110	S.D. dependent var	6.476822
S.E. of regression	0.970453	Sum squared resid	80.05118

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F-statistic	723.1462	Durbin-Watson stat	1.993905
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Table 2 displays the outcomes of the Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares (EGLS) model investigating the impact of corporate income tax (CIT) and tertiary education tax (TET) on net investing cash flow (NICF) of publicly listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The model shows a remarkably high adjusted R-squared of 0.9701, suggesting that around 97% of the variability in NICF is accounted for by the four tax variables present in the model. This indicates a strong model fit, implying that the selected tax variables collectively explain almost all the systematic variation in investment flows of firms. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.994 is nearly equal to 2, indicating low autocorrelation in the residuals, which improves the dependability of the coefficient estimates. Furthermore, the total F-statistic is extremely significant (Prob(F-statistic) = 0.0000), which confirms that the explanatory variables collectively exert a statistically significant influence on NICF at the 5% level.

The constant term ($C = -\text{₦}3,458,284,000$, $p = 0.0000$) signifies the base net investing cash flow when every tax variable equals zero. The negative coefficient suggests that without CIT and TET, the NICF of firms would remain negative, indicating a fundamental net disinvestment tendency among the analyzed industrial goods companies. Its importance at the 5% level verifies that this baseline effect is not a result of random fluctuations, offering a significant benchmark for understanding the marginal effects of the tax variables.

Hypothesis 1

H0₁: The income tax on companies does not significantly influence the net cash flow from investing activities of publicly traded industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

The CIT coefficient stands at -1.486032, accompanied by a p-value of 0.0000. This suggests that an increase of one unit in company income tax decreases net investing cash flow by around 1.49 units. The result is statistically significant at the 5% level since the p-value is less than 0.05. Consequently, H0₁ is dismissed, whereas the alternative hypothesis was accepted, indicating that corporate income tax significantly negatively impacts net investing cash flow in the examined firms.

Hypothesis II

H0₂: The tax on tertiary education does not have a meaningful impact on the net investing cash flow of publicly traded industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 2 displays a coefficient of 24.77412 for TET, accompanied by a p-value of 0.0000. This indicates that each extra unit of tertiary education tax leads to an approximate rise of 24.77 units in net investing cash flow, assuming other factors remain constant. The favorable trend might suggest that companies view TET as a tax linked to investment that offers long-term benefits, encouraging higher investment expenditures. Due to the highly significant p-value, H0₂ is dismissed, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This confirms that the tax on tertiary education positively impacts the net investing cash flow of publicly traded industrial goods companies..

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Discussion of Findings

The study found that company income tax negatively affects net investing cash flow, suggesting that higher CIT obligations diminish the cash available for reinvestment in industrial goods firms. This finding is supported by Odum (2025), Eyide et al. (2021), Aondover (2025), and Onwughai and Ofili (2025), who reported that CIT reduces investment or firm performance in various sectors. The negative effect can be attributed to CIT directly reducing after-tax profits, thereby limiting the funds firms can allocate toward new or ongoing investment projects.

The positive effect of tertiary education tax on net investing cash flow indicates that firms may view TET as a structured tax whose compliance can coincide with strategic planning of resources for investment. This finding aligns with studies by Onwughai and Ofili (2025), Omodero (2024), Olaoye and Fasanmi (2024), and Alpheaus et al. (2024), which show that TET can have positive or neutral effect on firm performance and investment when firms integrate tax obligations into financial planning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research determined the impact of corporate taxation on investment within publicly traded industrial goods companies in Nigeria, utilizing company income tax and tertiary education tax as the forms of corporate tax. The findings of this research emphasize the intricate impact that various corporate taxes have on investment actions among industrial goods companies in Nigeria, indicating that taxes do not consistently hinder capital growth but can also encourage it in specific situations. The research indicated that tertiary education taxes positively influence net investing cash flow, implying that certain tax responsibilities might motivate businesses to strategically manage resources, possibly through utilizing tax incentives, reinvesting profits, or refining financial strategies to improve long-term productivity. On the other hand, significant adverse impacts of corporate income tax suggest that elevated transactional and income-related tax pressures can diminish liquidity, raise operational expenses, and restrict the financial flexibility essential for companies to initiate new investments or grow their current operations. Consequently, the research highlights the nuanced relationship between fiscal policy tools and corporate financial conduct, demonstrating that taxation can either discourage or encourage investment actions based on the type of tax and the ways in which companies handle their resources to maintain growth and competitiveness in the industrial domain.

Recommendations

The research suggested that:

1. The Ministry of Finance ought to revise the scheduling and collection methods of corporate income tax to alleviate cash flow pressures on businesses, as the considerable negative impact on net investing cash flow suggests that existing CIT responsibilities could hinder firms' capacity to finance investment initiatives.
2. Corporate leaders and finance teams ought to incorporate TET planning into their long-term investment strategies, as the favorable impact on net investing cash flow indicates that adhering to TET can align with efficient resource allocation towards productive investment efforts

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